

ZDZW project, enabler of major digital manufacturing event that brought industry, technology, and research communities to Valencia

- The [Digital Manufacturing Industry Summit](#) (DMIS) was co-organized by the Zero Defect Manufacturing Platform and many other EU-funded projects such as [ZDZW](#).
- The conference brought together up to 250 stakeholders representing industry, technology, and academia and was hosted by the Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), one of the ZDZW partners.

On 25-27 April 2023, the Digital Manufacturing Industrial Summit (DMIS) took place in Valencia, Spain. The conference was organized jointly by the Zero-Defect Manufacturing Platform and a large pool of other EU funded research and innovation projects, including the Zero Defects, Zero Waste (ZDZW) project.

The aim of the summit was to facilitate cross-cutting discussion, co-operation, and networking between manufacturers, developers, researchers, and policy makers. The cornerstone of the event was discussion around how cutting-edge technologies are transforming modern manufacturing, moving from Industry 4.0 to 5.0, and the benefits of such a transformation, with a focus on achieving zero defects and zero waste in the manufacturing process, which is the main aim of the ZDZW project.

The networking conference covered a wide range of digital manufacturing topics, including zero defects and data quality, digital platforms and marketplaces, robotics and AI, and

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sustainability and resilience. Discussions were had around the key challenges around digital manufacturing. What works best in terms of further unlocking the Digital age and moving from Industry 4.0 to 5.0 whilst working for a greener and more efficient industry? What are the expectations of digital quality approaches? What part will manufacturing data spaces play? What is the impact of ethical AI on industry? What progress has been made on digital platforms in the European landscape? How will blockchain technologies impact manufacturing?

These questions were answered by linking together industry, technology, and research, by exploring the latest interpretations of concepts, and by sharing success stories and lessons learned with participating stakeholders.

More than 25 ZDZW members attended the event and actively participated in the conference based on their expertise. ZDZW led three sessions on quality assurance, zero defects and green manufacturing; moderated two round tables on policy recommendations to support non-destructive inspection (NDI) technologies and on green transition; and provided two keynotes and other speeches related to the project topics.

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Partners in the project

